

1 **Effects of bathing intensity, rainfall events, and location**
2 **on the recreational water quality of stream pools in**
3 **southern Ecuador**

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13 **HIGHLIGHTS:**

- 14 • Poor recreational water quality can impact public health and ecotourism
15 • Bathers, rainfall, and location determine recreational water quality
16 • Bathing diminishes microbiological water quality from upstream to downstream pools.
17 • Regulations and land-use practices can enhance recreational water quality.

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23

24 **Abstract**

25 Bathing in natural waters is a highly demanded recreational activity in tropical countries
26 because of climatic conditions and availability of bathing sites; but, do users know the
27 water quality of these sites? We determined the physicochemical and microbiological water
28 quality of a highly used bathing site in southern Ecuador. We assessed how bather
29 attendance, rainfall events, and pool location alters the recreational water quality (RWQ).
30 Most of the parameters measured in the stream pools did not accomplish the Ecuadorian
31 and international regulations for recreational water quality. Microbiological water quality
32 diminishes from upstream to downstream pools because of human activities and bathing
33 intensity having potential effects on bather health and eco-touristic development. We found
34 that an increase of bathers is strongly associated with a growing concentration of
35 *Escherichia coli*. It is suggested better land-use practices and review thoroughly the
36 Ecuadorian regulation to assure a healthy RWQ. Further efforts are needed to identify more
37 risky bathing sites, determine pollution sources, and establish a long-term monitoring
38 program to support the touristic development in countries looking for diversifying their
39 economy.

40 **Key words**

41 Recreational water pollution; Fecal coliform; *Escherichia coli*; gastrointestinal illness;
42 Tropical dry forest; Ecotourism

43

44 **1 Introduction**

45 Ecuador has a very rainy climate and is one of the South American countries with more
46 abundant water resources: $43,500 \text{ m}^3 \text{ inhab}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$. The availability of water is very
47 different across the Ecuadorian Andes due to the differences in rainfall. For instance, the
48 eastern slopes (Amazon basin) have a water availability of $82,900 \text{ m}^3 \text{ inhab}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$, while in
49 the western slopes (Pacific basin) diminishes to only $5,200 \text{ m}^3 \text{ inhab}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ (SENAGUA,
50 2012). The abundant rainfall, geology and the steep relief of the Ecuadorian Andes provide
51 the necessary conditions to form pools along rivers and streams. Those pools are used for
52 recreational activities contributing to the ecotourism industry, becoming an important
53 income for rural population living around protected areas in Ecuador (López-Rodríguez and
54 Rosado, 2017), and promoting the conservation of one of the most biodiverse countries in
55 the world (Myers et al., 2000).

56 On the other hand, when precipitation falls over agricultural land, runoff can wash
57 pathogens from the surface indirectly decreasing the microbiological water quality of the
58 streams. For instance, runoff from manure-fertilized pastures (Iñiguez-Armijos et al.,
59 2014). Moreover, sewage effluents can directly add more pathogens to streams (Knee and
60 Encalada, 2014). In both cases, such an impoverishing of the microbial water quality may
61 contribute to an increase of pathogens in recreational waters downstream becoming a public
62 health problem (Santiago-Rodriguez et al., 2012). The quality of recreational water can also
63 be affected by internal sources of pollution. Bathers act as a source of microorganisms,
64 principally by shedding microorganisms from their bodies and by resuspension of polluted
65 sand and sediment (Fewtrell and Kay, 2015; Phillip et al., 2009). This phenomenon

66 becomes more intense when there are many bathers, and the pools are narrow, deep and
67 with little water renewal (Kistemann et al., 2016).

68 This situation led developed countries and international institutions to write guidelines to
69 ensure the quality of water for recreational use and the health of its users. Examples are the
70 European Union with the Bathing Water Directive 2006/7/EC (European Council, 2006),
71 the United States of America (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2012) or
72 the United Nations (World Health Organization, 2003). Later, developing countries, like
73 Ecuador, drafted their regulations for recreational water quality (Ministerio del Ambiente
74 del Ecuador, 2015). However, the regulations are rarely enforced because the public
75 administrations lack the necessary resources to assure the quality of all types of water,
76 prioritizing potable water.

77 Once in the water, microorganisms can infect human beings by the ingestion of
78 contaminated water and bathing also, since microorganisms can enter the body through the
79 ears, nose, eyes or a skin wound (World Health Organization, 2003). Pathogenic
80 microorganisms are very diverse and include bacteria, viruses, and protozoans. For this
81 reason, it is common to use fecal indicator bacteria (FIB) whose presence is correlated with
82 the set of pathogenic microorganisms and their determination is easier, faster and cheaper
83 (Dhondia et al., 2014; Jacob et al., 2015; Sunger and Haas, 2015).

84 Several studies have concluded that the presence of pathogenic microorganisms in
85 recreational water increases the risk of gastrointestinal and dermatological diseases, in
86 addition to respiratory and ear and eye related diseases (Eregno et al., 2016; Fewtrell and
87 Kay, 2015). Epidemiological studies show a greater number of gastrointestinal diseases
88 among frequent bathers than among non-bathers (Kistemann et al., 2016). In developing

89 countries, diarrhea caused by microbiologically contaminated water are common and cause
90 2.2 million deaths per year (Montgomery and Elimelech, 2007).

91 The most common FIB are total coliforms, fecal coliforms, and *Escherichia coli*. Total
92 coliforms are defined as all facultative aerobic and anaerobic bacillus, Gram negative, non-
93 spore forming and fermenting lactose forming a gas at 35°C. They are not a health threat
94 itself, but an indicator of whether other potentially harmful bacteria may be present
95 (American Public Health Association, 2012). Total coliforms refer to the entire group, and
96 their origin does not have to be pathogenic, whereas fecal coliforms only include bacteria
97 of fecal origin (Okafor, 2011). Fecal coliforms are defined as gram-negative, non-
98 sporulating bacilli fermenting lactose with acid and gas production at 44.5°C. Fecal
99 coliforms are an indicator of possible contamination by sewage or other decaying debris.
100 The most representative species of the fecal coliform group is *E. coli*, that stands out as an
101 indicator since it can cause cystitis, peritonitis, meningitis, infections of the excretory
102 apparatus, mastitis, septicemia and pneumonia (Sunger and Haas, 2015). This fact has led
103 the US Environmental Protection Agency and the European Union to recommend the use of
104 *E. coli* (fecal coliform group) to analyze the microbiological quality of recreational waters
105 (Mwanamoki et al., 2014).

106 For these reasons, pathogenic microorganisms in recreational waters should be permanently
107 monitored. This type of monitoring ensures the health of users, promotes tourism and
108 contributes to sustainable management (Phillip et al., 2009). With all of this in mind, this
109 study aims to assess how recreational water quality of natural pools in a tropical dry forest
110 stream is modified along the longitudinal gradient, by bathers, and during rainfall. We
111 hypothesized that microbiological water quality decreases up-to-downstream pools, with

112 higher bathing intensity, and during rainfall events. We also determined the relationships
113 between the microbiological water quality and bathers in the stream pools, expecting an
114 increase in *E. coli* concentration with a higher number of bathers. Finally, we evaluated the
115 compliance to environmental regulations aimed to assure the recreational water quality in a
116 country like Ecuador, which is looking to strengthen the tourism industry.

117 **2 Materials and methods**

118 **2.1 Study site**

119 We conducted this study in a second order stream (Papalango stream) of the Catamayo-
120 Chira river basin located in the dry forest of southwestern Ecuador, 217 km far from the
121 city of Loja (Fig. 1). The climate of this region is influenced by dry air masses coming from
122 the Tumbesian Dry Region and by a low precipitation regime (Rollenbeck and Bendix,
123 2011). The annual mean temperature and precipitation in the study site are 23°C and 500
124 mm respectively, making the stream one of the most favorite natural places for bathing and
125 outdoor recreation. For that reason, around 14,000 people visit this stream annually
126 (Sánchez and Villareal, 2016). Papalango is a clear water stream presenting shallow fast-
127 flowing riffles in the upper section and several deep slow-flowing pools in the middle and
128 lower sections of the catchment. Because of size and accessibility, the pools located in the
129 lower section are the favorite sites for recreational use.

130 The native vegetation of the study area is represented by scrubland and seasonally dry
131 forest. However, this area holds an intensive agriculture such as most of southwestern
132 Ecuador (Tapia-Armijos et al., 2015). The upper section of the Papalango's catchment
133 shows a mixed land use of native vegetation, pastureland, and cropland. The middle section

134 is covered by native vegetation and a variety of crops, while the lower section is devoted to
135 cropland, mostly maize.

136 At the lower section of the Papalango's catchment, we selected four pools having different
137 intensity of recreational use (Fig. 1). The four pools were labeled from A to D, being the
138 pool A the most upstream site and pool D the most downstream site respectively. At pool
139 A, no recreational activities are carried out because of difficult access and dense vegetation.
140 The pool B is surrounded by low vegetation and access is only possible on foot, for this
141 reason, the recreational use of the site is moderate. The pool C shows the highest use by
142 bathers thanks to its easy access by car and new touristic infrastructure. The pool D has the
143 lowest recreational use since it is the furthestmost bathing site of the study area.

145 **Fig. 1.** Study area and location of the sampled pools. Photographs indicate the four studied
146 natural pools located from up (A) to downstream (D) reaches along a tropical dry forest
147 stream in southwestern Ecuador.

148 **2.2 Field procedures**

149 Sampling was conducted over eight dates before, during, and after Carnival celebration
150 from February to March in 2015. Sampling dates were divided equally between the high
151 (weekends and carnival days) and low (business days) attendance days, and between days
152 with and without rainfall events. On each sampling date, the pools were sampled three
153 times during the high demand period between 14:00 and 18:00 h. In total, each pool was
154 sampled 24 times during this study ($n = 96$). *In situ*, we determined water temperature, pH,
155 conductivity (Oakton PCTestr 35, USA), and dissolved oxygen (Sper Scientific DO Pen
156 850045, USA) using different portable probes. Water samples were taken in two sterilized
157 plastic containers from each pool at 30 cm depth. One sample (500 ml container) was used
158 for turbidity, phosphate, and nitrate determinations; while the other one (125 ml container)
159 was used for determining the concentration of total and fecal coliforms, and *E. coli*. Water
160 samples were transported in a dark cooler at 4°C to the laboratory and analyzed within two
161 hours of sample collection. Additionally, we quantified the number of bathers at each pool
162 during the field sampling.

163 **2.3 Laboratory procedures**

164 Water analyses were carried out in a laboratory located at 20 km far from the study site.
165 The infrastructure, equipment, and reagents of the laboratory are managed by a group of
166 municipalities situated in the dry forest region (Mancomunidad del Bosque Seco) with the
167 aim of monitoring water quality in this region.

168 Turbidity was measured according to the nephelometric method with a turbidimeter (Hach
169 2100N, USA) following the standard methods protocol 2130 B (APHA, 2012). The
170 turbidimeter was calibrated with standards supplied by the manufacturer. Turbidimeter cells

171 were rinsed three times with water of the sample. Cells with the sample were immersed in
172 an ultrasonic bath for 2 min before measurement to remove bubbles.

173 Phosphate measurements were carried out following the ascorbic acid method as described
174 in protocol Hach 8048, similar to method 4500-P-E of standard methods (APHA, 2012). A
175 Hach DR2800 spectrophotometer was calibrated at 880 nm with standard solutions
176 supplied by the manufacturer. 10 ml cells were filled with the samples in duplicate, Phosver
177 3 reagent (Hach, USA) was added in only one of the cells containing every sample leaving
178 the other duplicate as a blank. Cells were stirred for 30 s and allowed to stand for 2 min.
179 Next, blanks were inserted into the spectrophotometer followed by the reagent samples to
180 determine the concentration of phosphate.

181 Nitrate was determined using the Hach 8171 protocol, similar to method 4500-NO₃ E of
182 standard methods (APHA, 2012). The spectrophotometer was calibrated at 400 nm with
183 standards supplied by Merck (Germany). One cell of 25 ml was filled with deionized water
184 and other 25 ml cell with the sample. Then, the reagent Nitrover 5 (Hach, USA) was added,
185 and cells were stirred. Zero was set in the spectrophotometer with the blanks and samples
186 were measured.

187 Fecal coliforms were determined following the protocol 9222 E (APHA, 2012). 100 ml of
188 the sample was filtered. The filter was placed in a chromogenic agar for coliform bacteria.
189 The filter was incubated at 44°C for 24 hours. Positive colonies to β-galactosidase and d-β-
190 d-glucuronidase were counted.

191 Total coliforms and *E. coli* were determined following the protocol 9222 H (APHA, 2012).
192 100 ml of the sample was filtered. The filter was placed in a chromogenic agar (m-

193 ColiBlue24 Broth, Hach, USA) for both total coliforms and *E. coli*. The filter was
194 incubated at 35°C for 24 hours. Positive colonies in red (total coliforms) and blue (*E. coli*)
195 were counted.

196 **2.4 Data analysis**

197 The IDAHO water quality index, designed by Said and Stevens (2004), was calculated to
198 summarize in a single value the water quality at each pool based on four physicochemical
199 parameters (dissolved oxygen in % saturation, total phosphorus, specific conductance and
200 turbidity) and one microbiological (fecal coliforms) analyzed in this study (Table 1).

201 IDAHO index was calculated using the ICATest v1.0 software developed by Fernández et
202 al. (2001).

203 The mathematical expression for the IDAHO index is as follows

$$204 \quad \text{IDAHO index} = \log \frac{(\text{DO})^{1.5}}{(3.8)^{\text{TP}} (\text{Turb})^{0.15} (15)^{(\text{FCol}/1000)} + 0.14(\text{SC})^{0.5}}$$

205 where DO is the dissolved oxygen (% oxygen saturation), Turb is the turbidity
206 (Nephelometric turbidity units, NTU), TP is the total phosphates (mg/L⁻¹), FCol is the fecal
207 coliform bacteria (CFU·100 m/L⁻¹) and SC is the specific conductivity (μS/cm⁻¹ at 25°C).

208 The IDAHO index ranges from 0 to 3. The maximum quality value corresponds to 3 and
209 the minimum to 0. The value of the index is 3 in good quality waters with 100% DO,
210 turbidity less than 1 NTU, no TP, no FCol, and SC less than 5 μS/cm⁻¹. Values from 3 to 2
211 indicate an acceptable water quality. An IDAHO index below 2 points out that remediation
212 is needed and that one or two variables have deteriorated. Finally, the index is less than 1 if
213 most of the variables have deteriorated and water quality is poor (Said and Stevens, 2004).

214 To assess differences in the microbiological water quality, we constructed a matrix with the
215 values of each microbiological variable determined in the laboratory. The data were
216 arranged by the attendance of bathers (high vs. low), rainfall event (yes vs. no), and
217 spatially based on pools location (upstream vs. downstream). All analyses were performed
218 in the R environment (R Development Core Team, 2018).

219 We screened collinearity between microbiological variables using the Pearson's correlation
220 coefficient ('stats' package; R Development Core Team, 2017). Nonetheless, we did not
221 detect intercorrelated variables ($r < 60$). Mixed-effect models ('nlme' package; Pinheiro et
222 al. 2014) were used to assess variations in the microbiological variables. Thus, the data
223 matrix was analyzed in a nested design of three factors, and the sources of variation were
224 attendance (2 levels), rainfall event (2 levels), pool location (4 levels), and their
225 interactions. Attendance, rainfall event, and pool location were treated as fixed factors,
226 while sampling date was treated as a random factor. Mixed-effect models were fitted by
227 generalized least squares (GLS) using restricted maximum likelihood (REML) procedures.
228 Residuals were assessed by applying the Shapiro-Wilk test, and data were log-transformed
229 if needed (i.e. if the non-normal distribution was detected).

230 To assess the relationship between microbiological water quality and bathers, we pooled
231 the data and compared the concentrations of total and fecal coliforms, and *E. coli* against
232 the number of bathers by applying simple linear and nonlinear regressions ('stats' package;
233 R Development Core Team, 2017). Similarly, these three variables were analyzed against
234 the physicochemical parameters to determine further interactions. For all models, residuals
235 were assessed, and data were log-transformed if needed.

236 3 Results and discussion

237 3.1 Physicochemical parameters and IDAHO index

238 The physicochemical parameters and, therefore, the IDAHO index, are similar in the four
 239 pools analyzed (Table 1). The index ranged from 1.488 to 1.519 (maximum = 3) in the four
 240 pools analyzed, suggesting an intermediate water quality and that one or two variables have
 241 deteriorated (e.g. SC and fecal coliform).

242 **Table 1** Physicochemical and microbiological parameters (mean \pm SD) and IDAHO index
 243 measured in four natural pools of a tropical dry forest stream in southwestern Ecuador. The
 244 values for recreational waters limits according to the Ecuadorian regulation are indicated to
 245 the right of each parameter.

Variable	Pool A	Pool B	Pool C	Pool D	Recreational Water Quality Limit
Water temperature (°C)	22.4 \pm 0.6	22.4 \pm 0.6	23.3 \pm 0.7	23.8 \pm 1.0	-
pH	8.5 \pm 0.1	8.5 \pm 0.1	8.5 \pm 0.3	8.7 \pm 0.1	6.5-8.3
Specific conductivity (μ S/cm ⁻¹) ‡	173.6 \pm 34.0	173.7 \pm 35.4	197.2 \pm 45.1	202.0 \pm 46.1	-
O ₂ (mg/L ⁻¹)	6.4 \pm 0.6	6.4 \pm 0.5	6.2 \pm 0.7	6.2 \pm 0.6	-
O ₂ (%) ‡	80 \pm 7.5	80 \pm 6.3	76 \pm 8.8	76 \pm 7.5	80
Turbidity (NTU) ‡	21.7 \pm 18.4	22.7 \pm 18.6	27.2 \pm 15.6	27.9 \pm 14.8	-
Phosphate (mg/L ⁻¹) ‡	0.5 \pm 0.5	0.4 \pm 0.3	0.4 \pm 0.4	0.4 \pm 0.2	-
Nitrate (mg/L ⁻¹)	0.3 \pm 0.1	0.3 \pm 0.4	0.2 \pm 0.2	0.2 \pm 0.2	-
Total coliforms (CFU·100 mL ⁻¹)	3,025 \pm 982	3,133 \pm 1,517	3,499 \pm 841	3,408 \pm 801	2,000
Fecal coliforms (CFU·100 mL ⁻¹) ‡	219 \pm 123	273 \pm 164	569 \pm 515	517 \pm 349	200
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (CFU·100 mL ⁻¹)	171 \pm 73	160 \pm 64	389 \pm 159	286 \pm 91	-
IDAHO index	1.49	1.52	1.46	1.46	

246 ‡ Indicates the five variables used to calculate the IDAHO index.

247 Few physicochemical parameters are considered in recreational water regulations, which is
 248 normal considering that the most important water quality parameters for recreational waters

249 are microbiological (Bedri et al., 2016). As shown in Table 1, the Ecuadorian regulation of
250 recreational waters includes limits only for pH and O₂ (% sat), but exclude temperature,
251 conductivity, turbidity, nitrates or phosphates. Only recommends the total nitrogen and
252 total phosphorus ratio of 15:1. Nitrates and phosphates are not regulated because they are
253 relatively innocuous compounds for living beings. However, they can cause eutrophication
254 and remove oxygen from water when are present in large amounts and the right proportion.
255 Some global regulators, such as the EU or the USEPA, do not set limits for the
256 physicochemical parameters described in Table 1 for recreational waters (European
257 Council, 2006; United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2012).

258 The analyzed pools did not comply with the pH and O₂ (% sat) value limits, 8.3 and 80%,
259 respectively, given in the Ecuadorian regulation of recreational waters, i.e. they are
260 unsuitable for bathing (Table 1), although the variability in pool C for pH was higher. The
261 above pH limit was exceeded by a few tenths and showed an increase from up-to-
262 downstream pools. For this reason, monitoring the pH is recommended to ensure the
263 quality of bathing water and the safety of the bathers. Regarding O₂ (% sat), pools C and D
264 were below this threshold and pools A and B were on average exactly on the limit (80%).
265 So, they are considered uncompliant since many of the measures used to calculate that
266 average were below the limit given in the regulation.

267 Due to the lack of thresholds for physicochemical parameters in the regulation of
268 recreational waters, specific conductivity, turbidity, and nitrate were compared to
269 Ecuadorian, EU, and USEPA drinking water standards. Phosphate is not controlled in any
270 of these regulations for the reasons cited above and, therefore, no comparison is
271 established. Nitrate complied with the three drinking water standards, i.e. below 50 mg/L⁻¹

272 in the Ecuadorian, 50 mg/L^{-1} in EU, and 10 mg/L^{-1} in US regulations. Specific
273 conductivity, compared to the unique reference of the EU regulation, is considered of
274 excellent quality which is below $2,500 \text{ }\mu\text{S/cm}^{-1}$. On the other hand, turbidity did not comply
275 with the norms of potable water according to the single reference in the Ecuadorian
276 regulation of 5 NTU, in which it must be negligible. Despite this, these values are normal
277 for natural surface waters, and the difference with the regulations is explained because this
278 is a critical parameter for the consumer and treatments dedicated to the reduction of
279 turbidity are carried out in the water treatment plants. These values are very difficult to
280 reach without these treatments. Also, turbidity is not a dangerous parameter for the health
281 of people, so it does not pose a risk as microbiological parameters do.

282 **3.2 Microbiological parameters**

283 Results suggested that the microbiological water quality of the pools is not suitable for
284 bathing according to the Ecuadorian regulations of recreational waters (Ministerio del
285 Ambiente del Ecuador, 2015). According to Table 1, the maximum permissible limit of
286 $2,000 \text{ CFU}\cdot 100 \text{ mL}^{-1}$ of total coliforms was exceeded up to 3-fold in all the pools (Fig. 2),
287 and in most cases, exceeded the $200 \text{ CFU}\cdot 100 \text{ mL}^{-1}$ of fecal coliforms (Fig. 3). Also, *E. coli*
288 concentration in all pools (Fig. 4) was not suitable for bathing according to the USEPA
289 regulations (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2012), and the same
290 happened in pools C and D according to European regulations (European Council, 2006).

291

292 **Fig. 2.** Boxplot of the concentrations of total coliforms between bathers' attendance (high
 293 vs. low) and between rainfall events (no vs. yes) in natural pools located from up (A) to
 294 downstream (D) reaches along a tropical dry forest stream in southwestern Ecuador.
 295 Dashed horizontal line indicates the maximum permissible value for recreational waters
 296 according to the Ecuadorian regulation.

297 As with physicochemical parameters, the microbiological parameters included in the
 298 Ecuadorian, European and US regulations for recreational waters differ. Within the
 299 parameters analyzed, Ecuadorian regulations only contain limits for total and fecal
 300 coliforms, while European and US regulations only set a limit for *E. coli* as a bacteria with
 301 greater health risk within coliforms.

302 The results of microbiological parameters were disaggregated according to the attendance
 303 of bathers, rainfall events, and pool location (Table 2). The concentration of total coliforms
 304 did not differ significantly between the three factors assessed. However, significant
 305 interactions were observed between the attendance of bathers and pool location on the
 306 concentration of total coliforms. As shown in Fig. 2, all measured values of total coliforms
 307 ranged from 2,000 to 4,500 CFU·100 mL⁻¹ exceeding the Ecuadorian regulation for
 308 recreational waters. The values are very similar in all pools despite differences in the
 309 attendance of bathers and rainfall events. These data suggest that bathers are not the cause

310 of the high values of total coliforms in this stream. More research is needed to identify the
 311 sources of such number of coliforms or the factors causing this phenomenon.

312 **Table 2** Summary table of the mixed-effect models performed on concentrations of total
 313 and fecal coliforms and *Escherichia coli* in water samples from natural pools of a tropical
 314 dry forest stream in southwestern Ecuador. Water samples were analyzed between bather
 315 attendance (high and low), rainfall event (yes and no), pool location (from A to D).
 316 Numerator degrees of freedom (numdf), denominator degrees of freedom (dendf), *F*-
 317 statistic and *p*-values are shown (significant difference is indicated in bold).

Source of variation	numdf	dendf	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Total coliforms</i>				
Intercept	1	62	764.88	<0.001
Bather attendance (BA)	1	62	0.72	0.401
Rainfall event (RE)	1	62	0.4	0.528
Pool location (PL)	3	62	0.43	0.733
BA × RE	1	62	0.01	0.939
BA × PL	3	62	1.64	0.188
RE × PL	3	62	2.21	0.096
BA × RE × PL	3	62	1.59	0.200
<i>Fecal coliforms</i>				
Intercept	1	62	120.23	<0.001
Bather attendance (BA)	1	62	20.55	<0.001
Rainfall event (RE)	1	62	5.9	0.018
Pool location (PL)	3	62	5.91	0.001
BA × RE	1	62	0.02	0.958
BA × PL	3	62	3.54	0.020
RE × PL	3	62	1.16	0.331
BA × RE × PL	3	62	0.37	0.773
<i>Escherichia coli</i>				
Intercept	1	62	266.95	<0.001
Bather attendance (BA)	1	62	25.06	<0.001
Rainfall event (RE)	1	62	9.16	0.004
Pool location (PL)	3	62	29.09	<0.001
BA × RE	1	62	8.34	0.005
BA × PL	3	62	3.2	0.029
RE × PL	3	62	1.71	0.175
BA × RE × PL	3	62	1.14	0.340

318

319 Around 10-30% of the total coliforms found in the stream pools are fecal coliforms ($\approx 200-$
 320 $1,000 \text{ CFU} \cdot 100 \text{ mL}^{-1}$). As shown in Fig. 3, a large part of the fecal coliforms exceeds the
 321 Ecuadorian regulation for recreational waters. Also, the concentration of fecal coliforms
 322 was significantly higher during high attendance days and periods without rainfall events
 323 and increased significantly from pool A to pool D. The interaction between attendance of
 324 bathers, rainfall events and pool location on the concentration of fecal coliforms was
 325 significant. These results suggest that bathers may be increasing the concentration of fecal
 326 coliforms by removing sediments, having a similar outcome in those found in a small
 327 tropical stream in the Caribbean island of Trinidad, ranging $500-700 \text{ CFU} \cdot 100 \text{ mL}^{-1}$
 328 (Phillip et al., 2009). However, the authors reported higher numbers of fecal coliforms in
 329 the rainy season than in the dry season in contrast to this study. This situation can be
 330 explained by the fact that a higher number of bathers and the smaller size of the stream may
 331 potentially increase the concentration of fecal bacteria during the dry season.

332

333

334 **Fig. 3.** Boxplot of the concentrations of fecal coliforms between bathers' attendance (high
 335 vs. low) and between rainfall events (no vs. yes) in natural pools located from up (A) to
 336 downstream (D) reaches along a tropical dry forest stream in southwestern Ecuador.

337 Dashed horizontal line indicates the maximum permissible value for recreational waters
 338 according to the Ecuadorian regulation.

339 The concentration of *E. coli* was significantly higher during high attendance days and
 340 periods without rainfall events, and much higher in the pool C than in the others. There was
 341 only one significant interaction between attendance of bathers and rainfall events on *E. coli*
 342 concentration. As observed in Fig. 4, *E. coli* values are in the range of 50-550 CFU·100
 343 mL⁻¹, but also, they are showing more variability across the pools reaching the highest
 344 concentration in pool C which is the most used for bathers. According to the EU and US
 345 regulations, it is required calculating the 90th percentile of *E. coli* of the measurements
 346 recorded in each pool and its standard deviation to determine the recreational water quality.
 347 Once this percentile has been known, it was compared to the threshold of sufficient quality
 348 of the European regulation of 900 CFU·100 mL⁻¹, and the USEPA regulation for 36
 349 estimated illness per 1,000 bathers. Following this procedure, none of the pools comply
 350 with USEPA limit, while pools C (of 1,245 CFU·100 mL⁻¹) and D (965 CFU·100 mL⁻¹) do
 351 not meet the EU limits. These values assume that the risk of diseases associated with *E. coli*
 352 is high in this natural bathing site. *E. coli* was reported as the best predictor of
 353 gastrointestinal illness, above enterococci and other bacterial indicators (Wade et al., 2003).

354

355 **Fig. 4.** Boxplot of the concentrations of *Escherichia coli* between bathers' attendance (high
356 vs. low) and between rainfall events (no vs. yes) in natural pools located from up (A) to
357 downstream (D) reaches along a tropical dry forest stream in southwestern Ecuador.
358 Dashed horizontal line indicates the maximum permissible value for recreational waters
359 according to the European and US regulations. Ecuadorian regulation not applicable.

360 **3.3 Bacteria origin**

361 The bacteria studied in recreational waters can have different origins. One of them is the
362 presence of bathers in the pools, which would explain the significant differences of *E. coli*
363 between pools and attendance of bathers. It could also explain the difference between
364 rainfall events if considered that during the dry periods there were more bathers and
365 streamflow was lower, consequently that a smaller amount of *E. coli* could generate the
366 same concentrations. However, the differences found between rainfall events could not be
367 explained by other factors such as the rainfall-related runoff (Bedri et al., 2016), which can
368 drag microorganisms from livestock and agriculture in the Papalango catchment, since
369 during days without precipitation the concentrations of *E. coli* were greater than in rainy
370 days.

371 Fig. 4 shows an increase in the concentration of *E. coli* from pool A to B, and B to C,
372 followed by a decrease to pool D. This pattern behaves similarly to the intensity of
373 recreational use in these pools, suggesting that bathers are a potential source of this
374 bacteria. In this regard, we regressed the concentration of *E. coli* against the number of
375 bathers at the most used stream pools (i.e. B and C), showing a strong relationship between
376 both variables (Fig. 5). However, further research is recommended to determine the *E. coli*
377 variety (e.g. Enteropathogenic, Epec, Enterotoxigenic, Etec, enterohaemorrhagic, Ehec,

378 enteroinvasive, eiec, enteroaggregative, EAggEC, and diffuse adherent, Daec) and to
379 clarify its origin and possible health effects (American Public Health Association, 2012).

380

381 **Fig. 5.** Regression analysis between the concentration of *E. coli* and number of bathers at
382 the most used pools (B and C). The coefficient of determination (R^2) and significance (p -
383 value) of the regression are shown. Values for both variables are logarithmically
384 represented.

385 Luo et al. (2018) found a similar relationship in the National Nature Reserve for the
386 Chinese Giant Salamander in Zhangjiajie, Hunan Province, China. The authors suggested
387 that the rise in *E. coli* might be produced by increased organic matter availability due to lint
388 and other organic materials brought in by visitors, as also suggested by others (Ikner et al.,
389 2007). The same pattern was found by Phillip et al. (2009) in a small tropical stream in the
390 Caribbean island of Trinidad. The authors suggested that the increase in bacteria in the

391 areas with bathers could be due to the resuspension of bacteria attached to bottom sediment
392 by the bathers. However, *E. coli* is a bacteria known to have a high concentration in human
393 feces, which could also be a source in recreational waters (González-Leal, 2012).

394 Although fecal coliforms showed significant differences based on the three variables
395 studied (attendance of bathers, rainfall events, and pool location), results suggested that
396 bathers may not be the main source of bacteria, unlike with *E. coli*. In fact, the relationship
397 between the number of bathers and fecal coliforms was significantly weak ($R^2 = 0.12$),
398 despite the concentration of fecal coliforms always increased from up to downstream pools.
399 Therefore, further research is needed to elucidate whether other sources of microorganisms
400 are modifying the concentration of fecal coliforms.

401 In the case of total coliforms, no significant differences were found regarding attendance of
402 bathers, rainfall events, and pool location, suggesting that the origin of total coliforms
403 seems to be in some more stable over time sources located upstream of pool A (control).
404 This phenomenon would be possible with the pH (8.5-8.7) and temperature (22-24 °C) of
405 water, which are favorable for the growth of microorganisms.

406 There are diffuse sources along the Papalango catchment that could add pathogen
407 microorganisms to water. In this area, direct discharge of untreated sewage and effluents
408 from septic tanks to the streams are common, due to the small size of urban centers and the
409 lack of economic resources. These spills are well-known sources of coliforms and are more
410 stable over time (Santiago-Rodriguez et al., 2012). Therefore, the identification of sources
411 and remediation need immediate attention.

412 With regard to the interactions of bacteria with physicochemical parameters, we only found
413 a weak, but positive, relationship ($R^2 = 0.28$; $p < 0.001$) between *E. coli* and water
414 temperature. Higher growth rates of *E. coli* have been found to be positively correlated to
415 higher temperatures (Jang et al., 2017; Vital et al., 2008), indicating that warmer waters
416 may be an advantage for the proliferation of pathogenic organisms.

417 **4 Conclusions**

418 This study indicates that the recreational water quality of stream pools is associated with
419 multiple factors within a dry tropical landscape. Climate and bathing intensity alter the
420 concentrations of fecal bacteria reducing the microbiological water quality of the bathing
421 sites. Additionally, our findings suggest that human activities (e.g. farming and ranching)
422 along streams may lead into a top-down decreasing of the recreational water quality having
423 potential effects on bather's health and eco-touristic development. Nevertheless, the water
424 quality of streams can be enhanced or maintained by increasing forest cover, improving
425 land-use management, and protecting riparian vegetation (Iñiguez-Armijos et al., 2014).
426 For instance, sediments, nutrients, and pathogens washed away by runoff can be trapped in
427 the riparian vegetation. Livestock exclusion along streams can significantly reduce direct
428 bacteria inputs to water.

429 In this study, we also detected a deficiency in the Ecuadorian regulations to control and
430 monitoring recreational water quality. The inclusion of *E. coli* and other pathogens in the
431 national regulations is a pressing task to support local governments when mitigation
432 strategies are applied.

433 We believe that the problems showed here might occur in other bathing sites in Ecuador (or
434 other tropical countries). Identify the problematic bathing sites, determine the pollution
435 sources and a long-term monitoring program are needed to sustain and enhance the touristic
436 development in countries looking for diversifying their economy.

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